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English Literature Teaching-Learning Strategy of Bangladesh: Viewing in the Light of Outcome Based Education (OBE) Curriculum

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Abstract: The study aims to focus on the English literature teaching-learning strategy of Bangladesh in developing four language skills and in analyzing any literary text critically in the light of OBE curriculum so that learners can enable them to be fit for jobs and entrepreneurship. The study also pays attention to the role of different genres of literature (i.e. poetry, novel, and drama) in facilitating language teaching-learning process. Reading literature is more likely to provide the students with the scope to get interesting resources with authentic context which may motivate them strongly for language learning and to be skilled in competing for a job or entrepreneurship. In addition, reading literature in native language is helpful to understand the inner meaning of a text. In this study, everything will focus on OBE curriculum frameworks, because this way one may easily adapt skills for future. The research in consideration will be qualitative in nature and it will mostly consult secondary sources of data.

Keywords: OBE Curriculum, Bloom Taxonomy, Rubric, and Skills

1.1 Introduction

In Bangladesh, English literature, and language are taught individually, and even EFL/SEL is also taught individually. As a result, those who study literature are not paying concentration in language and they often become frustrated not to understand literary texts. On the other hand, those who study language and linguistic are very good in speaking with correct accent but their mental development is poor to judge the overall scenario of a society as they do not have any literary ideas. Moreover, the language students sometimes fail to apply the appropriate examples to express their view.

English literature can be used in the EFL classroom at universities in Bangladesh. Different genres of literature such as drama, epic, poetry, novel and non-fiction should be given importance in English curriculum. Hişmanoğlu (2005) emphasizes the use of literature as a popular technique for teaching both basic language skills (i.e. reading, writing, listening and speaking) and language areas (i.e. vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation). Primarily this study aims to focus on the application of English literature in developing four language skills of the university level English learners. Then, the use of literary passages in teaching a foreign or second language will be discussed broadly. Moreover, the study will also concentrate on the issues in terms of vocabulary and grammar. Lastly, this might be able to enhance the opportunity to incorporate literature more in the curriculum following Outcome Based Education (OBE) Curriculum.

1.2 Background of the Study

Language is an inevitable element of human life (Ashrafuzzaman & Alam, 2017). No communication happens without language and English has become an imperative language in which people from all around the world can communicate. In this world of globalization, English language skills can provide plenty of opportunities. Having a good command over English Language gives learners a handful of opportunity to enjoy their life and career (Sultana & Ashrafuzzaman, 2016; Babu et al., 2014; Roshid & Webb, 2013; Ehsan et al., 2011; Coleman, 2010; Ainy, 2007). But a problem arises when the learners are frequently asked to emphasize on accuracy rather than fluency. As a result, they face a lot of problems while they need to communicate orally because they take much time to express their views. On the other hand, if one emphasizes on fluency, they cannot communicate correctly in writing. A blended learning of language-literature can overcome the problem. Often the hardest part of a language teacher's job is finding the right balance between fluency and accuracy related teaching in the classroom, as both are equally important. However, the student's reason for studying the language will sometimes dictate the balance to some extent. For example, adults who are learning English for nonacademic reasons are likely to be more concerned with fluency, while young learners studying for exams are more likely to be concerned with accuracy ("Fluency versus Accuracy"). Aside from taking a course, one very easy way to improve one's accuracy in English is to read any type of English material on a daily basis. Whether it is a novel, a non-fiction book, a newspaper or magazine, reading is an easy yet effective way to absorb the nuances of English grammar and punctuation. ("Fluency vs Accuracy")

Linguists opine that there is an intimate relationship between language and literature (Violetta-Irene, 2015). According to Brumfit and Ronald (1986), literature is "an ally of language". Moreover, Maley (1989) identified some of the causes for recognizing literature as a forceful resource in the way of learning language that include universality, non-triviality, personal relevance, variety, interest, economy and suggestive power, ambiguity etc. Sage (1987) stated that the use of literature in language teaching might be a valuable and interesting strategy. Furthermore, Mason and Krashen (2004) observe that literature is a more interesting medium than traditional methods in teaching language. Learners can attain various features of a particular language from literary works. Literature exposes learners to a wide range of vocabularies, grammar, and pronunciation. Literature familiarizes learners to the practical use of language and universal themes related with human psyche. There are numerous ways to utilize diversified literary texts in language learning that are fruitful and less intimidating. Shahid (2016) opines that literature can be used as a technique for teaching both basic language skills (i.e. reading, writing, listening and speaking) and language areas (i.e. vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation).

The theories in language teaching-learning have been changed over time due to the influence of linguistic, psychological, educational and political perspectives derived from "a mixture of assertion, theory, observation and

experiment” (Hall & Cook, 2012). Developing new methods and techniques is a challenging task for foreign language teachers. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) Approach welcomes the use of real-life situations in using language whenever possible. Structured drills used in audio-lingual method make the teaching process monotonous (Gangola, 2015). In the grammar translation method, literature was the central component. Literary texts of the target language were read and translated, used as examples of good writing and “illustrations of the grammatical rules” (Duff & Maley 1990). However, for last two decades, literature has been considered as an influential tool in foreign language teaching and curriculum (Babae & Yahya, 2014). Duff and Maley (1990) also that for the last two decades, the use of literature has been regarded as a precious instrument in language teaching. Moreover, for the last couples of years, University Grants Commission (UGC), and Bangladesh Accreditation Council (BAC) have been working to ensure students’ perspectives in learning-teaching language applying Outcome Based Education (OBE) Curriculum. So, one way Lecture Method or Grammar Translation Method (GTM) is rejected and Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is encouraged for growing students’ interest in learning both language and literature.

1.3 Rationale of the study

In recent years, literature has become a basic component and source of authentic texts of the language curriculum. It provides real life materials and acts as a beneficial complement to such materials. Brumfit and Carter (1986) affirm the point that a literary text is an authentic text which we can respond to straightforwardly. Among language educators, there has been a hot debate regarding how, when, where, and why literature should be incorporated in ESL/EFL curriculum. Vigorous discussions have been projected for how literature and ESL/EFL instruction can be combined for the benefits of students and teachers. This has led to a flourishing of interesting ideas, learning, and improved instruction for all. Many teachers consider the use of literature in language teaching as an interesting and worthy concern (Sage 1987). Besides, a number of language learners prefer to read novels, poetry, short stories etc. in their native languages. Reading a full novel in a second language can be extremely nerve-racking and overwhelming (Jewett, 2017). Such a text firmly grasps the reader’s thoughts and makes scopes for the examination of language as well (Gangola, 2015).

Literature helps students to build up interpretative abilities. It is an excellent source for increasing students’ abilities to infer meaning and to make interpretations (Gangola, 2015 & Lazar 1993). Literature in a language classroom provides opportunities for the learners to comment and rationalize themselves. By using a literary text, a language class can be made sparkling and inspiring (Violetta-Irene, 2015). In addition, it can play a vital role in the communicative language teaching approach. Literature of a target language is read, translated, and used as samples of good writing and “illustrations of the grammatical rules” (Duff & Maley 1990). It also enables students to get familiar with universal issues. According to Collie and Slater (1990), literature offers a bountiful and extremely varied body of written material that deals with ongoing human issues (Gangola, 2015). By means of integrated approach in teaching, students can find out the skills for each grade level in the context of quality literature.

1.4 Research questions

The study has decided to find answer to three questions. The questions are:

1. Why is literature necessary for developing language skills of the students?
2. How can literature be used effectively in language teaching?

3. Why OBE Curriculum is interesting to the students for enhancing their language skills?

1.5 Objectives of the study:

This paper underscores how the use of literature in a language classroom makes language learning easier and more entertaining. It focuses on the implications of using English literature for teaching English language and explores its advantages as well as challenges that both the language teacher and learners may come across. The paper specially shows how the areas of language learning can benefit when a literary text is used in a language classroom.

2.1 Discussion

Literature has been a subject of study at different levels of education in many countries, but in recent time it has been given much emphasis in the EFL classroom (Kaşlıoğlu & Ersin, 2018). The use of literary texts in foreign language teaching has greatly been increased over the last few years. The role of literature in the language classrooms was questioned during the period of 1960 to 1980. The 1970's and early 1980's approaches were communicative and emphasized on practical functions of English language. During the 1980's there was a comeback of interest in literature and language teaching. The interest in literature as a valuable tool in language teaching was raised two decades ago (Hall, 2005; Duff & Maley, 1990). It is in line with the communicative approaches as it considers authentic communicative conditions in the way of teaching second language (Sanz & Fernández, 1997). A couple of writers such as Brumfit and Carter (1986) and Lazar (1993) stated that language used in literature is an ordinary language including linguistic qualities such as metaphors, similes, poetic lexis, and so on. We cannot consider these features as literature specific because they also appear in common language application.

Literary texts must be chosen according to the learners' requirements, goals, life experiences, cultural background, and language level. According to Collie and Slater (1987), a work must not exceed student's reading proficiency. Interest, appeal, and relevance are all important. The following are to characterize Collie and Slater's approach to choose literary texts:

- Implementing various student-centered activities such as role-plays, interview, questionnaires, pair work, group work, opinion sharing, information gap, visuals, and others.
- Introducing the assets of knowledge with the group as it can prop up individuals' feedback and understanding. Group members must conduct a task within a short period of time that occurs on a page of literary text.
- Sharing opinions at the time of working individually or in group might be a great way for the introvert students to be more open.
- Using target language that may be helpful to convey effective response either non-verbally or by partial language skills.
- Combining language and literature.

(How these should be assessed by OBE Assessment tools is given in Apndix-1.)

Collie and Slater (1990) and Maley (1989) state four main causes which lead a language teacher to use literature in the classroom. These are valuable authentic material, cultural enrichment, language enrichment and personal involvement. Regarding the valuable authentic material, Lestari Setyowati (2017) opines:

Nowadays there is a growing attention for using literature in language teaching. Literary works can be considered as authentic because its creation is not meant for language teaching. Unfortunately, not many language teachers are interested to use literature to teach language. This paper is intended to describe the advantages of using literary works for language teaching based on the writer's experience of using them in language classroom. As authentic materials, literary works are rich in content, language use, idiom, and vocabulary. ... The use of literary works in language classroom can train the student's critical thinking. It can also serve as the exposure of the language used in real communication. When literature is carefully chosen and prepared, it can serve as a powerful tool to help students to master their language learning.

Moreover, other factors such as-universality, non-triviality, personal relevance, variety, interest, economy and suggestive power and ambiguity are powerful resources in the classroom context.

Carter and Long (1991) describe three models for using literature: the cultural model, the language model and the personal growth model. Each model is a representation of different propensities in relation with methodology and classroom practice. They also express that literature is indispensable for personal development.

- The literary text is regarded as a product in the cultural model. Learners get acquainted with the different cultural and artistic heritage through literature.
- Students build up their language through inventive exercises of literature. The main aims are based on learners and their actions.
- The personal growth model is the basis of the students' engagement with literary texts. Students learn via literature as to how to welcome and appraise cultural artifacts. It is more student-centered replica with impetus aims.

Duff and Maley (1992) suggest many appealing actions for teacher trainers, practicing teachers, and teachers who are interested in using literary texts in ELT. The key aim of Maley's approach is to use literary texts as a resource for stimulating language activities. They also advice the teachers to involve students in the group concerning literary texts. Dymešová (2006) states that literary texts are important at three levels: linguistic (texts are full of different styles, registers, genres), methodological (literary texts manufacture interlinkage among learners), and motivational (the sensation of literary texts is a strong motivator).

Helton, Asamani and Thomas (1998) illustrate the educational benefits of novels as follows: arising learners' imagination, attaining problem solving ability, developing oral and written language skills. It serves a holistic learning approach so that learners can get involved with reading process promptly. On the other hand, David Hill (1993) presents three stages approach: these are- raising-awareness, text contact and aftermath stage. This approach is conducive to making learners more insightful and motivated to learn language. The authors Clandfield & Duncan (2005) view that literature is an authentic material for language learning due to its educational value along with encouraging social interaction among learners. Overall language has been changed according to geographical location, different social contexts, different social settings and professions. In this case literature makes the students familiar to a wide range of language varieties such as sociolects, regional dialects, jargon, idiolects etc. Hence, literature incorporates sociolinguistic aspects in the way of teaching target language (Shahid, 2016) and educates the learners to grow professionally (Carter & Long, 1991; Van, 2009; Yeasmin et al., 2011).

This study has developed the 'conceptual framework for studying language learning through literature' by reviewing different literatures and sought out these features in this study.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework-Language Learning Through Literature
(The diagram is quoted from Ashrafuzzaman et al, 2021)

The conceptual framework represents the relationship among literary texts and language learning, reasons for using literature in English classes, teaching-learning approaches, methods and development of language skills of students. This framework also focuses on literature, effective teaching of language, students' choice, benefits of different genres of literature (i.e. poetry, short fiction, drama and novel) for teaching-learning process and problems faced by language teachers within the area of teaching English through literature.

The above statement clearly shows that traditionally set up goals from teachers' perspective is not acceptable to achieve the target. To reach the goal, the teaching-learning language must set up from students' position (for CLO, see Apendix-1).

Another important thing should be considered here from the student's side. Most of the language students' view is to be involved in any multinational institutions or to communicate with the foreign delegates. So, companies are becoming more global as they have to deal with wide range of countries and English is listed as an essential skill for

more and more jobs. Hence, to get a good job and to study abroad, it is necessary to learn English. Here “learn English” means to have adequate knowledge of vocabulary and their usages.

Three examples are given here so that it becomes clear which example should be more effective for teaching-learning language. One is an ordinary example of a paragraph writing that only focuses the writing skills but it can cover few new vocabularies; whereas, the second one is taken from a short story by James Joyce and the third is a poem by Jibananda Das.

Adolescence

Adolescence is a changing stage of physical and physiological development that happens during the period between childhood and adulthood. This is an important part of life. This is a really critical period of life. In adolescence, girls and boys float in a very vibrant and fantasy world. Thus everything looks vibrant to them. That is why they will go wide. Adolescence may be a time of risk. (“Paragraph on Adolescence”)

Araby

James Joyce

North Richmond Street being blind, was a quiet street except at the hour when the Christian Brothers' School set the boys free. An uninhabited house of two storeys stood at the blind end, detached from its neighbours in a square ground The other houses of the street, conscious of decent lives within them, gazed at one another with brown imperturbable faces. (“Araby”)

A poem “Banalata Sen” (see Appendix-3) by Jibanananda Das. Banalata Sen in “Banalata Sen” is an imaginary character who is supposed to belong to Natore, a district in Bangladesh, and the character is so known to people of all ages in Bangladesh that many people still think Ms. Banalata actually exists in real life and one can meet her in Natore. It has become such a trend that if asked what Natore is famous for, people would readily add the name of Banalata Sen.

According to Turker (1991), “[t]he successes, of course, in using literature greatly depends on the selection of texts which will not be difficult on either linguistic or conceptual level.” Therefore, the language teacher should choose the text carefully, considering grammatical, linguistic and literary difficulties. Besides, literary texts should include the structures and vocabulary previously learned by the learners.

Thus, learners need to develop some general skills in order to develop their writing. That is why they need help in particular areas. Some of the general skills which learners require to develop their writing are- vocabulary, structure, spelling, organization, linking expression, punctuation, paragraphing, style of language, presentation, and coherence. These can be developed through a number of different types of writing tasks. Instead of engaging learners in writing just essays and paragraphs all the time teachers can use following tasks to create interest and variety as suggested by Pincas (1982), Harmer 2003), and Ur (2003).

- Writing response to a poem, film, and story: These can be used because they can be interesting and motivating. These activities can also help in developing reading and listening skills.

- Narrating incidents: This can be an interesting task and can help to develop narrative strategy. Teachers can use pictures or newspapers and magazines for this kind of activity.
...
- Describing people and places: Learners can describe people they know such as parents, friends, teachers, or a well-known figure. They can also describe places they have visited or seen or read in a literary text. These can help in developing descriptive strategy.
...
- Writing poems or stories: These can be fun and motivating tasks for imaginative learners and may be done once in three months. (Sinha, July 2011-June 2012)

Some other suggestions are given by a good number of researchers as well in making learning language through literature effective. Regarding the matter, McRae, 1991, & Ainy, 2208) opines that:

Nothing can be more interesting than literary materials, which have stories and characters that the students can relate to their lives. In fact, “a good choice would be any text that encourages or invites interaction with the world of ideas, a text that ‘affirms, confirms, and expands the indispensable human capacity to read the real world.

And Tazin Ahmed (2012) suggests:

Once the learners start finding literary material used in language classes interesting, only then their analytical power in the English language will improve largely. Moreover, their vocabulary and pronunciation skills will further develop as the language of literary material is essentially context-oriented, comprehensive, authentic and real-life like apart from being figurative or ornamental. (For more clarification, see CLOs of Appendix-1)

So, it is true that without making the lesson interesting, no student will pay attention in learning anything else. According to Krashen (1987), “[t]he best methods are therefore those that supply ‘comprehensible input’ in low anxiety situations, containing messages that students really want to hear.” In other words, students learn best when the material that is used is interesting and when they can exploit the material to improve their language further in terms of vocabulary, pronunciations and grammar. He [Krashen] (1985,1993,1999) states, “the language experience needs to be contextualized and comprehensible” and the learners needs to be “motivated, relaxed, positive and engaged.” (Arnold 1999; Tomlinson in Abraham, 2010).

3.1 Conclusion:

Literature plays a significant role in effective teaching-learning process whether English is regarded as a second or foreign language. It provides students with an incomparably rich source of authentic material. In Bangladesh, literature is a monumental part of education which acts as determinant factor for student’s personal development. In addition, it helps them to understand different cultures and society, and provides them with insight into history, people’s behavior and attitudes. Literary texts help the students to activate their imagination and develop their emotions. Furthermore, findings of the study recommend that curriculum should be redesigned by compiling more literature and adding student centered teaching methods. However, there is lack of objectives defining the role of literature in ESL/EFL. Students prefer to read novel, poetry and science fiction and a mixture of different types of texts which are most beneficial for developing their language skills in accordance with the textbooks they use. Teacher has an important role in teaching English through literature. They should select the appropriate language teaching methods, teaching

techniques, and classroom activities which ought to be relevant to the aim and objectives of teaching-learning activities along with academic text. Selected books must be relevant to the life experiences, emotions, or dreams of learners. For this reason, both pre-service and in-service training should be included for their professional development.

However, a large number of language experts have questioned why and how literature should be embodied in language curriculum. Many language instructors have faced several troubles while teaching language through literature. First, there are a small number of appropriate pedagogical materials used for teaching language with the help of literature. Second, there have not been sufficient ground works in the field of literature for teaching in the language curriculum. Third, no adequate purposes have been found to define the significance of literature in language classrooms (Babae & Yahya, 2014). This study will be helpful for policy makers, curriculum specialists, students and teachers to realize the benefits of literature for developing English language skills at the university level in the context of Bangladesh.

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Appendix-1 (Part-C)

(According to the UGC format, it is prepared)

Course Code (Following BNQF): ENG 2211
Course Title: Introduction to Literature: Drama
Credits: 03

Rational of the Course:

Introduction to Literature: Drama introduces the students to dramatic literature making them familiar with the terminology and methods for analyzing and evaluating drama along with a detailed history of the development of dramatic literature. This course is essential in the context of literature as it enlightens the students about the genre of drama and shows what it does and how the elements work together to make a piece of drama and what to look for when reading which in turn helps them to develop a number of transferable skills to be applicable in personal and professional sphere.

Course Objectives: The course, Introduction to Literature: Drama, intends-

- to introduce the students to the stages in the development, the structure and distinctive characteristics of different forms of drama as tragedy, comedy, satire, and tragicomedy with a focus on English drama.
- to make the students understand the terminology and identify all the technical devices related to drama.
- to develop effective communication skill in the students to be applied in diverse situations through their familiarity with different dramatic texts.
- to enable the students produce documents using relevant technological knowledge.
- to give the students the scope to apply their knowledge of genre, formal elements, and secondary materials in interpreting and analyzing drama texts.
- to make the students familiar to diversified culture through the exploration of different drama texts ultimately leading to the growth of a set of social and ethical values.

Course Contents:

Origin and Stages of Development in Drama: Discussion on the origins and the evolution of drama with a special focus on English drama (The circumstances associated to the emergence of drama, history of Greek, Roman drama, history of different stages of development in English Drama)

Structure and Characteristics of Drama: The structure and distinctive characteristics and elements of drama (Plot, character, setting, theme, style etc.)

Forms and Variations of Drama: *Different forms of drama as tragedy, comedy, and tragicomedy and their different variations (classical tragedy, revenge tragedy, modern tragedy, romantic comedy, farce, satire, restoration comedy etc.)*

Literary Terms Related to Drama: *All the terms and literary devices related to dramatic literature (Act, scene, aside, chorus, comic relief, catharsis, hamartia, hubris, catharsis, soliloquy, monologue, exposition, climax, denouement, poetic justice three unities etc.)*

Application of Methods and Literary Tools in Interpreting a Drama Text:

- (i) *Reading, discussing, and interpreting the drama texts included in the syllabus namely J.M. Synge's Riders to the Sea, William Shakespeare's The Merchant of Venice, and G.B. Shaw's Arms and the Man.*
- (ii) *Applying the methods and literary tools in analysing the aforementioned drama texts that would include discussing the major themes and core issues, identifying the characteristics of the particular genre in consideration (tragedy, comedy, and tragi-comedy etc.), the use of different dramatic devices and relevant literary tools.*

Review and Comparative Analysis of the Dramas Taught:

- (ii) *Review of all the drama texts included in the syllabus (J.M. Synge's Rider's to the Sea, William Shakespeare's The Merchant of Venice, and G.B. Shaw's Arms and the Man)*
- (iii) *A comparative analysis of the drama texts concerned based on their genre, themes and the core ideas.*

Text Books:

Synge, J.M. (2009). *Riders to the Sea*. BiblioLife.

Shakespeare, W. (1994) *The Merchant of Venice*. Longman.

Shaw, G. B.(1937). *Arms and the Man*. MA.

Abrams, M H. (1999) and Geoffrey G. Harpham. *A Glossary of Literary Terms*. Thomson Wadsworth,.

Programme Learning Outcomes (PLOs): After the successful completion of the programme, the learners will acquire the following abilities to:

PLO 1	Demonstrate excellent communication skills in English in diverse contexts
PLO 2	Develop a variety of transferable and employable skills through effective utilization of necessary technological resources in academic, personal and professional levels
PLO 3	Efficiently read, analyze, interpret, appreciate and undertake research in English language, literature, applied linguistics, ELT & interdisciplinary field of studies .
PLO 4	Grow sense of ethics and practices of socio-moral values both in personal and professional life
PLO 5	Have knowledge and understanding of English language in use, master pieces of English and American literature from different periods, postcolonial and cultural studies Have knowledge and understanding of English language, literature and cultural studies in practical applications

Course Learning Outcomes: At the end of the course, the students will be able to-

CLO 1	Recognize different stages of development, the structure, and distinctive characteristics of drama with a special focus on English drama
CLO 2	Identify and differentiate among such forms of drama as tragedy, comedy, satire, and tragicomedy
CLO 3	Interpret in dramatic literature such elements as character, action, theme, symbolism, irony, and terminology related to dramatic literature
CLO 4	Demonstrate strong communication skills in English as a result of active participation in diverse presentation activities relevant to drama using relevant technological knowledge
CLO 5	Apply the knowledge of genre, formal elements, and secondary materials in interpreting and analyzing drama texts
CLO 6	Appraise different drama texts and create a comparative analysis of these texts based on their genre, themes and the core ideas
CLO 7	Show a deep sense of social as well as ethical values through the exposure to different drama texts from diversified culture and contexts

Mapping of Course Outcomes to Program Outcomes-

	PLO1	PLO2	PLO3	PLO4	PLO5	PLO6
CLO1					✓	
CLO2			✓		✓	
CLO3			✓		✓	
CLO4	✓	✓				
CLO5					✓	✓
CLO6	✓		✓			✓
CLO7				✓		

Mapping Course Learning Outcomes (CLOs) with the Teaching-Learning & Assessment Strategy

CLOs	Teaching-Learning Strategy	Assessment Strategy
CLO 1	Lecture discussion with multimedia, interactive discussion, and question-answer sessions	Instructor-created definitive quiz
CLO 2	Lecture discussion with multimedia, interactive discussion, and question-answer sessions	Instructor-created definitive quiz, Formal Written Examination
CLO 3	Lecture discussion with multimedia, video presentation, and white-board Illustration	Oral presentation and written test consisting short analytical questions, Formal Written Examination
CLO 4	Diverse group tasks with peer feedbacks	Multimedia presentation
CLO 5	Lecture discussion with multimedia, concept formation, and peer feedbacks	Individual assignment on related broad analytical topics, Formal Written Examination
CLO 6	Lecture discussion with multimedia, concept formation, group tasks, and peer feedbacks	Group assignment on related broad analytical topics, Formal Written Examination
CLO 7	Interactive group discussion, guided and shared thinking, concept mapping, and self-assessment	Oral presentation and relevant written tests on evaluating particular situations in the prescribed texts from multiple perspectives

Appendix-3**Banalata Sen****Jibanananda Das**

For a thousand years I have walked the ways of the world,
From Sinhala's Sea to Malaya's in night's darkness,
Far did I roam. In Vimbisar and Ashok's ash-grey world
Was I present; farther off, in distant Vidarba city's darkness,
I, a tired soul, around me, life's turbulent, foaming ocean,
Finally found some bliss with Natore's Banalata Sen

Her hair was full of the darkness of a distant
Vidisha night, Her face was filigreed with
Sravasti's artwork. As in a far-off sea,
The ship-wrecked mariner, lonely, and no relief in sight,
Sees in a cinnamon isle sings of a lush grass-green valley,
Did I see her in darkness; said she, "Where had you been?"
Raising her eyes, so bird's nest like, Natore's Banalata Sen

At the end of the day, with the soft sound of dew,
Night falls; the kite wipes the sun's smells from its wings;
The world's colors fade; fireflies light up the world anew;
Time to wrap up work and get set for the telling of tales;
All birds home — rivers too — life's mart close again;
What remains is darkness and facing me — Banalata Sen!

(Translated from Bengali into English by Fakrul Alam)